

MIBIREM – Toolbox for Microbiome based Remediation

Deliverable 1.3

Data management plan version 2

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1 Summary

The purpose of task T1.4 is data management, particularly setting up and updating a data management plan. The project data management plan was updated at project month 36 which is reported in this deliverable. This document assists consortium members on high-quality data management in compliance with funder requirement:

- strategy of data management
- general measure of data management
- summary of data expected and re-used in the project
- application of FAIR principles to data produced during the project
- handling other research outputs (digital like software or protocols and physical output)
- strategies for data storage, allocation of resources and data security
- activity plan for data management
- Table with Datasets and other results, including 1 dataset underlying 1 scientific publication from the project created in P2

Disclaimer: The document does not in any way overrule the Grant Agreement (including its associated Annexes) and the Consortium Agreement.

2 Introduction

Bioremediation is a cost-effective and eco-friendly way to remediate sites polluted with organic contaminants. A successful application of bioremediation requires the understanding and control of the microbial networks that lead to degradation of contaminants. The MIBIREM project strives for adapting and streamlining microbiome science to the needs of applications, to exploit microbiomes for bioremediation, creating and applying a TOOLBOX to identify, analyse, cultivate and up-scale microbiomes, while ensuring safety and policy alignment.

In the MIBIREM project, 12 international partners perform research together in 8 work packages over a period of 4.5 years. This does not only require good project management but also a well organised data management. This includes foremost the data management plan (DMP), but also other work performed by the data management group. All partners benefit from good data management as it provides guidance on data storage, data publication, meta-data standards, etc.

Data management (DM) is part of work package WP1 as task T1.4, where all partners are involved. For T1.4, a DM group was formed with one representative from each project partner at least. The DM group meets to discuss open points on data management and takes decisions on common DM strategies. This is taken in agreement with legal data privacy regulations in consultation of the GDPR, the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Activities of the DM are reported in section 3.

A first version of the data management plan (DMP) was published in deliverable D1.2. The project data management plan was now updated at project month 36 which is reported in section 4 of this deliverable. Significant updates to the first version will be highlighted in section 3.5.

We perform Intellectual property (IP) management on generated datasets in task 7.3 (WP7). IP management is led by RTDS to avoid conflicts of interest, as RTDS will not own any results /IP generated in MIBIREM. IP management started during proposal preparation with a confidentiality agreement signed by all partners. Project results and their readiness for exploitation and partner contributions are assessed to clarify ownership. At the end of MIBIREM, a results ownership list (ROL) including taken or recommended IP protection measures will be included in D7.4. For all results, the possibility to protect IP and commercially exploit them is analysed before they are disseminated. IP management does not only look at key exploitable results (KERs), but at all results generated in MIBIREM. Data and software are covered by copyright; most are/will be freely available under specific licences (e.g. Creative Commons CC-BY). The specifics are outlined in the Consortium Agreement.

3 Data management activities

3.1 Data management group

We have a data management group in place since the start of the project where each project partner is represented. The DM group is supported by Research Data Management Support Staff of Utrecht University (UU). The DM group meets regularly to assess the status of the DMP, dissemination and publication of data as well as addressing current issues related to data management. Each meeting is documented including minutes being checked and approved by all participants. Meeting material and minutes are stored in the MIBIREM intranet (Sharepoint) available to all project partners throughout the entire project duration. Aspects of data management addressed by the data management group include:

- Maintain the DMP. Details on the content and updates of the DMP are provided in the following sections.
- DMP Data Collection Tables: we have two overview tables concerning project related data:
 - Reused data: *DMP_Data_Produced_VX.xlsx* (where the VX stands for version number X)
 - Produced data: *DMP_Data_Produced_VX.xlsx* (where the VX stands for version number X)
 The tables summarize all relevant information. They are available to all consortium members in the Sharepoint Intranet. The tables are regularly updated and given a new version number.
- Establishment and use of project related data repository: We make use of the UU managed data portal YODA (<https://geo.yoda.uu.nl>). External partners (i.e. Non-UU researchers) to join with a web-interface to access it. YODA provides the options to store and publish large amounts of (research) data with meta-data. A short introduction course on usage at YODA was given to all partners at the consortium meeting in M12.

- Data file templates for field sampling data: One of the first tasks performed in the DM group was the collaborative setup of data file templates for field sampling data based on experiences and needs of all partners. The process was aligned with metadata standards used in the project. Sampling data of the MIBIREM field sites has been transformed to the template format and are stored at YODA together with documentation (readme-files) for access by every group partner and long-term preservation also for potential use in the prediction tool (WP4) and the MIBIREM TOOLBOX post-project.

This work was also formalized as Milestone of T1.4 with the agreement of all partners on standard data formats.

- Lab sample naming strategy: During the project, samples (from the field and the lab) are exchanged between partners for further research. This brought up the issue of having a common and comprehensible strategy for sample naming. In several DM group meetings, we identified a common procedure to develop a standard "MIBIREM sample name" which is meant for simplifying exchange of samples and for unified data storage. Key aspects are: (i) the base of the name is the field sample name (see also Handbook, T1.1; Deliverable

D1.4); (ii) we distinguish major experimental types by capital letter shortcut, sample settings by 3 digit number, replicates by minor letter (if applicable), time steps (if applicable) by letter T+2-digit number.

3.2 Data management plan update

The data management plan is in place over the entire period of the project. We make use of the online-tool DMP-online (<https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk>). The DMP in this online tool was updated in month 36 (for this deliverable) and saved in the project administration repositories with related data. The final version will be prepared at month 54 at the end of the project.

We make use of the Horizon Europe Template, Version 1.0 (05 May 2021) provided in the DMP-online tool. It provides a list of questions on the main topics:

1. Data summary
2. FAIR data
3. Other research outputs
4. Allocation of resources
5. Data security
6. Ethics
7. Other issues

We address all these questions to outline the details of the DMP. This will be the content of section 4 with subsections structured following the main topics and providing the questions as well as our answers to them.

Beside editorial updates to the text, we highlight in the following significant updates to the DMP, version 1, project month 6 as provided in deliverable D1.2:

- Section 4.2.1: providing examples of data produced in project findable online
- Section 4.7: adding subsection on data versioning
- Annex: current versions of data tables "DMP_Data_Reused_V2.xlsx" and "DMP_Data_Produced_V2.xlsx".

4 Updated DMP

4.1 Data summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?

Data will be reused in the project. The two main sources of existing data reused in MIBIREM is data from preliminary investigations at the project field sites as well as databases on microbiological and genetic information. Details on the reused data sets are selected in a table "DMP_Data_Reused_VX.xlsx" being accessible by all Consortium members. The current version (V2) is added to the Annex. The table outlines type and description of the data, as well as owner, source, formats, software required, maximum size, number of data files, purpose of use in the MIBIREM project, metadata standards, storage location, linked publications, accessibility and licence.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

Data types and formats of reused data can be found in the table "DMP_Data_Reused_V2.xlsx" (in the Annex). A similar table "DMP_Data_Produced_V2.xlsx" (in the Annex) was set up collecting all data-management relevant aspects. When data is produced during the project, the information on the data sets are specified in the table. We foresee research data to be newly produced in the project of the following origins with types and formats:

- Laboratory experimental (raw) data on
 - analytical data
 - microbial biomass
 - sequencing data
 - genomic data
 - community analysis data
 - gene quantification
 - list of bacteria and cultures
 - list of functional genes
 - list of qPCR primers
 - (additional) numerical lab data
 - lab journal and protocols

Formats: csv/.biom/.fastq/.fasta/.xlsx/.txt/.doc/.docx/hand written notes
- Field - experimental data:
 - site descriptions, like sedimentary descriptions, hydrological parameters, biogeochemical conditions
 - On-site parameters (e.g. groundwater temperature, pH, oxygen content, etc.)
 - measured concentrations of contaminants and other chemical compounds
 - coordinates of sampling points

Formats: csv/.xlsx/.txt/.doc/.docx/handwritten notes
- Numerical data/Processed data:
 - statistical output data & results visualisation
Format: .csv/.tsv/.tiff/.jpeg/.png/.pdf/.svg/.rmd/.RData/.qmd
 - Software implementation data
Format: .r/.py/.ipynb/.sh
 - Simulation output:
Format: .vtk, .csv, .pdf

Non-scientific data produced in the project include documents on:

- Activity plans, project descriptions, contracts, templates and guidelines, meeting protocols, presentations
- DMP
- website

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The purpose of each data set is specified in the tables "DMP_Data_Reused_V2.xlsx" and "DMP_Data_Produced_V2.xlsx" (in the Annex).

The general purpose of generating sequencing data is to gain novel information on bacterial consortia. The data is interpreted in combination with the metadata to understand the functioning of a bacterial consortium. This also includes statistical analysis (processed data) and modelling (numerical data). All these data will provide new insights into the behaviour of microbiological processes and dependencies in the subsurface. They are used to find solutions for enhancing bioremediation which is the purpose of the project.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The number of files and size of each data set is specified in the tables "DMP_Data_Reused_V2.xlsx" and "DMP_Data_Produced_V2.xlsx" (in the Annex).

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The origin of each data set is specified in the tables "DMP_Data_Reused_V2.xlsx" and "DMP_Data_Produced_V2.xlsx" (in the Annex).

The research data (newly) generated during the project originates from research performed by the project partners through:

- sampling of field site conditions
- experiments (raw data)
- interpretations/visualisations of experimental data (processed data)
- implementation of algorithms (data interpretation methods)
- modelling output (predictions based on observation data)
- documentation data produced by researcher (manuscripts)

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

- other researchers
- stakeholders
- public
- Companies

4.2 FAIR data

4.2.1 Making data findable

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

All research data sets produced during the project will be findable through a unique identifier (UID). Data will either be published directly with a persistent identifier (DOI), in repositories/databases (providing UIDs) or along a scientific publication (with DOI), e.g. in the supporting material or with link to an open archive. We foresee for the different types of research data during the project:

- Experimental (raw) data: direct publication of the data set (with DOI) or deposition into a public repository providing unique identifier (e.g. sequence accession numbers), for instance:
 - [HCH \(Hexachlorocyclohexane\) degrading microbiota](#) and its [Temporal evolution](#) at NCBI
 - [Study on soil and groundwater bacterial diversity of petroleum hydrocarbon contaminated sites in Europe](#) at NCBI
- Processed experimental data: published in scientific articles.

- Numerical data: direct publication of the data set (with DOI)

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Newly created data sets will be provided with rich metadata.

As a collaborative project with research groups from various disciplines, we expect data of various kinds. As for all the project related disciplines metadata standards exist, we will make use of them.

For sequencing data, we will follow the metadata standards of the NCBI repositories NCBI Genbank and NCBI SRA as these are the standard discipline archives/repositories/databases (see also questions at 5.2) for depositing nucleotide sequences and raw sequencing data.

For one, NCBI uses the metadata standard "BioSample Data Model" to store metadata associated with biological samples. The BioSample Data Model is a standardised format for describing biological samples and their associated metadata, including sample identifiers, organism names, sample attributes, and other relevant information. BioSample Data Model is compatible with other metadata standards, such as MIAME (Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment) and MIGS/MIMS (Minimum Information about a Genome Sequence/Minimum Information about a Metagenome Sequence).

The SRA metadata describes the technical aspects of sequencing experiments: the sequencing libraries, preparation techniques and data files. Most of descriptive information is captured at the level of the SRA EXPERIMENT and will be displayed in the public record.

Moreover, SRA provides specialised bioinformatic tools, (SRA Toolkit 3.0.3¹). The tools facilitate deposit, conservation, identification and management of raw sequencing data, related metadata and also elaboration: The SRA Toolkit and SDK from NCBI is a collection of tools and libraries for using data in the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC²). The INSDC is a long-standing foundational initiative that operates between DDBJ (DNA DataBank of Japan), ENA (European Nucleotide Archive) and NCBI. INSDC covers the spectrum of data raw reads, through alignments and assemblies to functional annotation, enriched with contextual information relating to samples and experimental configurations.

Otherwise, we will make use of the common metadata standard "DataCite". This is also the one Zenodo's metadata is compliant with (again see also questions at 2.2 on repositories).

The outlined metadata standards guide the design of the standard file formats. The Handbook for sampling and sample treatment (T1.1, D1.4) is aligned with the metadata standards to guarantee data usability for all partners and avoid data loss due to a lack of documentation.

Details on the metadata standards are specified for each data set after publication in Table "DMP_Data_Produced_V2.xlsx", Annex.

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Keywords will be provided in the metadata according to the scientific domain-discipline, each dataset is related with. In this way we can ensure that interested parties can find our datasets.

¹<https://github.com/ncbi/sra-tools#the-sra-toolkit>

² <https://www.insdc.org/>

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

The metadata for our datasets will comply with the "Datacite v4" and "Dublin Core" metadata standards and will be offered in file formats (.xml, .json) that can be harvested and indexed.

In addition, Zenodo, which also serves as repository for publishing data of our project, facilitates any metadata harvesting and indexing with the use of the OAI-PMH protocol (Open Archives Initiative's Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) and its own REST API.

4.2.2 Making data accessible

Making data accessible – Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

The research data produced in the project will be accessible in trusted repositories. Following the terms of the Grant Agreement all data will be open access, unless it is for commercial exploitation or contrary to any other constraints by data (co-)owner. In particular, site owners engaged in MIBIREM can request the site data collected by the project to be confidential for safety and business reasons.

We will use trusted repositories:

- Zenodo being a general purpose repository. Here a project specific community for MIBIREM has been set up.
- ENA (European Nucleotide Archive) and NCBI Genbank and NCBI SRA (Sequence Read Archive) being domain repositories, i.e. a trusted repository established for the specific research domain of microbiology and bioinformatics.

The consortium agreed on using the listed repositories with Zenodo as a major repository to bundle all project data. However, the use of ENA and NCBI for genomic and sequencing data is agreed within the group given several reasons:

- Using NCBI/ENA increase re-usability of the produced research data:
 - NCBI and ENA are the most widely used and recognized repositories for sequencing data with a high level of recognition and acceptance (which cannot be provided by the multi-purpose repository Zenodo).
 - open-source software (e.g. source code deposited on GitHub) to access information is optimised on their application to NCBI/ENA.
 - NCBI offers specialised data management tools (SRA ToolKit v.3.0.3) designated for retrieving and reusing data.
- Some discipline specific research journals require authors to deposit their sequence data in one of the discipline specific repositories (ENA, NCBI, DDBJ).

Details on the used repository are specified for each data set after publication in Table "DMP_Data_Produced_V2.xlsx", Annex.

Making data accessible - Repository: Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

We explored the arrangements of the repositories. As stated, a Zenodo community for MIBIREM has been setup:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/mibirem/?page=1&size=20>

It allows all partners to deposit data at unlimited size.

Making data accessible - Repository: Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes, the mainly used repository (Zenodo) for our project provides by default an unique identifier (DOI) to every paper/data publication, ensuring the accessibility of our datasets on this platform.

Data published in ENA and/or NCBI SRA also is provided a unique identifier, like DOI or BioProject and sequence accession numbers.

Making data accessible – Data: Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

We follow the principle ‘as open as possible but as closed as necessary’. Most research data produced in the project will be openly accessible. Following the terms of the Grant Agreement (Annex 5) all data will be open access unless it is for commercial exploitation.

We expect that data produced solely by research groups of the consortium will be shared openly. Industry partners in the consortium indicated that opening specific data goes against their legitimate commercial interests. Research includes field sampling at contaminated sites owned by third parties. Some of the gathered data will be subject to restrictions due to legal and contractual reasons. This includes:

- Data on exact composition of the solution(s) used for remediation at sites as industry partners have commercial interest in this.
- Data on the exact procedure of culture production used for remediation at sites as industry partners have commercial interest in this.
- Protocols used to generate evolution data will be restricted due to commercial interests of industry partners. They will not be accessible within the consortium nor outside the consortium. On a case-specific basis we will evaluate if it is possible to publish data-subsets, like part of the protocol.
- Data on adaptive laboratory evolution (key performance indicator, diversity data - sequencing data, pictures - protocols used to generate the evolution data) will be restricted as this is commercially-sensitive information.
- Restrictions may apply to data collected by MIBIREM partners as well as data from 3rd parties (i.e. contaminated field site owners) when there is no consent for public disclosure of such data. We will consider making part of the data available or after anonymising site specific data. The process will be evaluated in adherence to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

When a produced dataset applies to restricted access conditions, these will be explained and put into context with constraints as per the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement (4.5 GDPR compliance) in the detailed data description in the Table of produced data (Annex).

Making data accessible – Data: If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Time embargos for data publication or protection of intellectual property (e.g. patents) are not expected for most of the produced research data.

However, for all results the possibility to protect Intellectual Property (IP) and commercially exploit them will be analysed before they are disseminated – this also includes data generated within the project. IP management will not only look at key exploitable results (KERs), but at all results generated in MIBIREM.

We anticipate few cases of data produced in the project which will be made accessible after a time embargo as they are of interest for patents which need time to carefully evaluate. The reason for the embargo is thus commercial exploitation. This concerns:

- microbiomes for bioremediation
- direct evolution equipment and developments on adaptive laboratory evolution (key performance indicator, diversity data - sequencing data, pictures - protocols used to generate the evolution data)

- single bacterial strains (must be evaluated under cost/benefit considerations)

Making data accessible – Data: Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?

As we plan to publish research data in established repositories, there will be a free and standardised access protocol.

For instance, data published in the Zenodo community can be accessed directly through downloading using the DOI and link.

Making data accessible – Data: If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

For produced research data, which is subject to restrictions on use, the data set owner will manage the access to the data. For restricted data sets we use the storage facilities specified below. They are all based on the principle of "need-to-know", meaning that only users who require access to the data for their work or tasks are authorised to access it. Every data user can access-log in these facilities with personal-institutional credentials. The owner of the restricted data set will decide how to share the data at different levels (e.g. read only, editor, co-owner) by providing access if requested.

We follow this procedure already for the project documentation/management data which is restricted to project members. Access is by registration on the and authorization through the project manager.

When a dataset applies to restricted access conditions, access arrangement during and after project end will be specified for the data set. A summary of that will be included in the Table "DMP_Data_Produced_V2.xlsx" (Annex).

Making data accessible – Data: How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Open-access data set will not request the identity of the person accessing the data.

For restricted data sets we use the storage facilities specified below. They are all based on the principle of "need-to-know", meaning that only users who require access to the data for their work or tasks are authorised to access it. Every data user can access-log in these facilities with personal-institutional credentials. The owner of the data set will provide authorization.

Making data accessible – Data: Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

We do not expect personal or sensitive (research) data to be produced in the project. If data applies to restricted access this will be handled as outlined before. We thus do not see the need for a data access committee.

Making data accessible – Metadata: Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

We plan to make metadata openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0. At this stage, we do not foresee exceptions. In case of any exception we will clarify why. We will use metadata community standards which will enable users to access the data and increase its findability.

Making data accessible – Metadata: How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Published data will be available and findable long-term. This will be ensured by publishing it in trusted long-term maintained repositories and journals. The same holds for meta-data.

Making data accessible – Metadata: Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We expect a large amount of data which requires software to access and efficiently read the data (e.g. sequencing data). This will be clearly documented and referenced in the metadata.

In case the needed software is open source and published (e.g. on GitHub, referenced with DOI), we will provide reference. If the software which is needed to access the data, is developed alongside the data it will be either published separately and referenced or included (if not published stand-alone). If the respective software is a commercial software or subject to restricted licence, it will not be possible to include it.

4.2.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

As part of the project task DMP, we will collaboratively set up data file templates. We seek to use preferable formats not restricted to commercial software such as .txt/.pdf/.odt for Text, .csv./Rdata for quantitative data, .jpg/.tiff for images.

We will use metadata standards of the individual disciplines to guarantee that variables are exactly defined:

- Common metadata standards such as Datacite 4.0 & Dublin Core
- ENA metadata standard
- For genomics data we will follow the MIxS checklist (<https://gensc.org/mixs/>).

The meta data standard is also depending on the repository where data will be preserved or shared. For instance, we will follow Zenodo's best effort principles. For making data interoperable this includes that metadata uses a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation such as the JSON scheme as internal representation of metadata.

The use of established metadata standards (including vocabularies, formats and methodologies) will also ensure that data is interoperable between project partner and other interested user.

Making data interoperable: In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

We do not expect the need to use uncommon ontologies nor are we planning to produce specific ontologies or vocabularies in this project.

Making data interoperable: Will your data include qualified references[1] to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

[1]A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Where applicable, produced research data will include qualified references to other data.

When research results/data builds up on each other, contextual knowledge will be provided. This holds e.g. for publication of results in scientific publications. Their used and produced data will be linked and with qualified references.

We will also use qualified references and cross-references to outline chains of data dependency and linked data. This will be facilitated by publishing the data within one Zenodo community which is planned for a large part of the data.

4.2.4 Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Depending on the data type we will provide documentation which facilitates validation of data analysis and re-use. We make use of readme files, codebooks and other measures for data management. Details on the methodology will be also documented in research papers. Most information will be provided in the method sections. We will also make use of Supporting Material which are common for scientific articles to provide detailed documentation if required. This way we ensure that research data can be validated and is reusable.

Modelling and coding data will be documented following state-of-the art standards. The prediction tool packages ([MiBiPreT](#)) are public available to facilitate validation and re-use of the data.

Increase data re-use: Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licences, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

We expect most of the data to be freely available in the public domain (open-access repositories) to allow re-use. We will only restrict data if it is subject to commercial use. Details on restricted data are outlined above.

Licences for data sharing and re-use remain subject to the project partners who produced the data. Data licensing will be arranged in accordance with the Grant Agreement following e.g. Creative Commons, Open Data Commons. We expect:

- CC-BY or CC-BY-NC-SA: for sequencing data
- Apache-2.0 or MIT for software/simulation data, e.g. produced by UGent and UU

Increase data re-use: Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Openly published data will be usable by third parties, during and after the end of the project. This will apply to most of the processed data (results and visualisations) as well as developed software and simulation data.

Raw data produced during the project with restricted re-usability (depending on licence) will not be usable by third parties. This will e.g. apply to field observation data from specific contaminated field sites where site owners hold the rights and refrain from data publication for specific reasons, like safety issues.

Raw data on microbiome analysis will be published and reusable by third parties during and after project end.

Increase data re-use: Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

The provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards. This will be documented in READMEs, publications as well as in the meta data provided to the published data set on repositories. For instance, all data and metadata uploaded to Zenodo is traceable to a registered Zenodo user. But we will make sure that the original authors of the published work are described in the metadata as well.

Increase data re-use: Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

We assure data quality through

- data collection following the handbook for sampling and sample treatment (developed during the project WP1, T1.1, D1.4)
- sample analysis following a unified procedure (preferably all performed at the same lab)
- use of data templates (developed during the project, WP1, T1.4)

- documentation of data with metadata following community standards as well as meta-data standards of targeted repositories for publication
- review of data within the DM subgroup

Increase data re-use: Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

Besides the management of research data, we will also address the management of other research outputs, such as conference/workshop contributions, software development and physical research output like bacteria strains.

We will also address aspects related to allocation of resources and data security. Ethical aspects do not apply here, as the research data is not related to personal data. See section 6.

4.3 Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

The principles outlined in the DMP for research data will similarly applied to digital research output (not being data), such as:

- protocols: results are the "Handbook for sampling and sample treatment" developed in WP1 (T1.1; D1.4)
- software: results are the prediction tool developed in WP4.
- models: is partially developed for the sites under investigation, also in co-development of the prediction tool (WP4)
- workflows: expected results are the bioremediation toolbox (MIBIREM-TOOLBOX innovation) in WP6.

Physical research output we expect includes:

- physical samples, such as soil samples (WP1)
- laboratory samples, such as microcosms (W2)
- degrading microbiomes (WP2)
- bacteria strains (WP3)

A selection of strains that are active degraders are publicly deposited in the BCCM/LMG Bacteria Collection. Internet links between the culture collection catalogue and the genome database and the genome sequences are provided. Whole consortia that actively degrade selected pollutants will be publicly deposited in the BCCM/LMG Bacteria Collection.

The procedure leading to deposition (including whole genome sequence determination and analysis) is based on standards developed within the project (Task 3.1 of WP3). This includes setting quality-control standards for public deposit, preservation and distribution of bioremediation microbiomes.

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for reuse, in line with the FAIR principles.

The questions addressing the FAIR principles will be similarly applied to digital research output. This digital research output is and will be published, similar to data, in trusted repositories, with unique identifier (e.g. DOI), open access, with metadata and proper documentation (README etc.). Code and software are created following good coding practice to make it reusable and interoperable. For instance all software is and will be developed within GitHub Organizations in publicly available repositories which are documented including Readmes. Data and software are

covered by copyright; most are expected to be made freely available under specific licences (e.g. Creative Commons CC-BY). The Prediction tool software developed in WP4 is freely available but licensed for use to end-users.

For the physical output of bacteria strains, we consider the applicable elements of the FAIR principles during the process of preparation and public deposition in the BCCM/LMG Bacteria Collection. Project task 3.1 (WP3) focuses on setting quality-control standards for public deposit, preservation and distribution of bioremediation microbiomes. There the elements of the FAIR principles find consideration. For instance, management of metadata is done to conform with the MIRRI (Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure) principles (<https://www.mirri.org/mirri-microbial-resources/>).

4.4 Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

Several project teams were awarded with money for open access publication costs. This applies to:

- CNRS: 10 000€ for 4 articles at 2500€ each. CNRS already released 1 scientific publication, listed in the Annex.
- UGENT: 10 000€ for 4 articles at 2500€ each.
- SENSA: 2000 € for 1 article.
- Utrecht University (UU): 10 000€ for 4 articles at 2500€ each.

Utrecht University was awarded with 7500€ for data management to cover expenses for hardware, software and personnel to support sharing and preservation of the data. From this amount, we cover proportional costs for support by professional data stewards of UU. Furthermore, we allocate at least 2000€ to be spent on hardware expenses for providing a central project storage with the UU-institutional repository YODA which can be also used by external partners. The mutual decision to make use of Yoda as central project data storage was taken in M13 as part of Milestone MS3. Extending the default storage capacity of 1TB cost 4€ per TB and month. Thus, to store e.g. additional 10TB of data we need 2160€ (10TB for 54 months at 4€/TB/Month).

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

The cost of data publication will be covered by the money granted to the project as specified above. The same holds for the cost specified above on hardware, software and personnel to support sharing and preservation of the data as well as data management.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

All project groups are involved in the data management. However, the lead on the DMP is by Utrecht University through Alraune Zech. She is directly supported through a DMP work group consisting of one representative for each project partner. In addition, specialised personnel (data stewards) from Utrecht University provide assistance to the general data management tasks of this project and ensure the compliance of the data with the Open Science and FAIR principles.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

We will ensure long term preservation of research data by publishing it on trusted and long-time operating repositories. As a consortium we agree to use Zenodo (multi-purpose repository) and NCBI (domain specific repository) as both provide different advantages in use (see above). If unforeseen circumstances require partners to publish in other repositories, this will be discussed in the data management subgroup.

For Zenodo, a project community has already been established. This allows all project partners to publish and deposit data without data size restriction. For both Zenodo and NCBI, we therefore do not expect any additional costs for the publication and long-time preservation.

We formed a Data management group where each project partner is represented. We meet regularly to assess the status of the DMP, assess the dissemination of data and its potential publication. We will assist researchers in the project to prepare the data according to project needs as well as following the FAIR principles. This way one person from each research group takes the responsibility of administering and supervising the whole process of data management.

We are going to use open formats e.g. .csv, .txt because these formats facilitate the interoperability and re-usability of our data by others which will also contribute to long-term preservation. File formats will also be specified during development of standard file formats for sample data as part of the data management (Task 1.4, WP1).

Before each research publication, a selection will be made with regard to which data is useful for long-time preservation. The published datasets will be linked with the according publication and will be given a persistent identifier e.g. DOI. A data selection will be made based on reproducibility and re-use purposes. During our project we have agreed on following the next guidelines for each data publication:

- Raw and processed data included in:
 - The data in the Zenodo repository will be preserved for the lifetime of the repository. As stated by Zenodo on their "retention period": *Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.* (<https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>)
 - The data deposited to NCBI or ENA will be preserved for the lifetime of the repository/archive. As stated by ENA, "All database records submitted to the INSDC [International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration, including NCBI Genbank and ENA] will remain permanently accessible as part of the scientific record". (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/about/policies>)
- Physical samples will be stored in the storage of the sampling partner and/or the partner performing the analysis of the data. For instance, physical samples collected along evolution experiments and analysed by LESAFFRE, will be stored at LESAFFRE's location and preserved for the duration of the project, plus another 2 years after project end. Physical samples processed by UGENT (enriched cultures for isolation in WP2 and microbial consortium in WP3) will be stored in the lab and preserved indefinitely (or until use) as part of the UGent database.
- Bacteria strains will be publicly deposited in the BCCM/LMG Bacteria Collection and will also be preserved indefinitely.
- Digital research output will be published on Zenodo following the preservation specifics as outlined above.

4.5 Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Produced or processed research data (during the production process, i.e. premature to publication) from this project will be securely stored by all project partners in individual storage facility solutions, such

- cloud solutions
- institutional repositories
- institutional servers/databases

Cloud solutions used by partners are:

- Microsoft OneDrive (AIT, UU, UNIPI)
- Microsoft Sharepoint (UGENT, DND, Tauw, RTDS)
- Google Drive (UHAS, LESAFFRE)

All the partners using cloud solutions have special agreements with providers on privacy and information security legislation and guidelines to comply with the GDPR, e.g. storage of data on European servers.

Institutional repositories, clouds, servers and databases:

- YODA (UU)
- OTELo Cloud NC (CNRS)
- MySQL servers (UGENT)
- SENSEA server (SENSEA)

The institutional storage solutions are part of the University/company infrastructure and comply with privacy and security policies of the concerning institutes.

These facilities allow storage of large data volumes that are backed up on a daily basis, in specialised data centres, not only ensuring the preservation of the data in a trustworthy and dependable location, but also effectively minimising the risk of data loss in the event of any system malfunction or crash.

The used storage facility solutions handle data access based on the principle of "need-to-know". This means that only users who require access to the data for their work or tasks are authorised to access it. Every data user can access-log in these facilities with personal-institutional credentials.

The analysed or resulted data of the project will be published on well-known and trusted repositories (i.e. Zenodo, NCBI etc., see above) and therefore they will be secure through the security provisions of these platforms.

While transfer of sensitive research data does not apply in the project, the use of secure institutional systems can provide assurance against any unanticipated attempts at data tampering, whether deliberate or accidental in nature.

4.6 Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

We foresee no ethical issues for data sharing within the project. As there are no human participants involved in this project, the project will not be submitted for ethical assessments.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

This is not applicable in this project as we are not planning to conduct any surveys.

4.7 Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

No. We only follow the data management procedures provided by the European Commission (Horizon Europe Template).

Versioning of datasets

As the list of datasets in the Annex shows, MIBIREM is also using existing research datasets in the frame of its project activities. It is thus important that such research data provided "as background" for project implementation is utilised and labelled correctly. The DMP recommends MIBIREM consortium members to implement a versioning system to

adequately trace the updated/enhanced versions of their research datasets, which derive from such data collected “as background”. The [OpenAIRE](#) guidelines on raw data, backup and versioning continue to provide useful pointers on how to properly implement versioning of research data in EU-funded collaborative projects:

“During the course of analysing data, it is likely that you will create several derivatives of the working copy, sometimes even automatically through scripts. Whether one of these versions is valuable and should be kept for long-term preservation is completely dependent on the data owner. However, it is recommended that versions are frequently monitored to discard those that are not required for verification, reproducibility, or transparency, amongst others. You might want to keep all versions, but these can be very large files which will take up valuable storage space. Versioning is a key part of any workflow and appropriate measures should be taken to enable this, whether it is simply versioning through slight alterations to file names or using dedicated version control tools. The latter are also commonly used in large projects to allow multiple users to check-out and check-in the same file after making alterations. This also allows provenance, i.e. documenting or inspecting the history of changes. Just as with backups, the first step is to find out what your organisation provides.”

The pro-active and consistent versioning of research datasets within MIBIREM also serves to facilitate reporting on research datasets, especially in the frame of the (periodic) updates of the list of research datasets in the project.

5 Activity plan for data management

Task	Activities	Resp.	By when / Status
T1.4 Data management (M1-M54), UU <u>Contributors:</u> All	Regular meetings of DMP subgroup	UU, all	M36-M54
	Mid period internal data management plan update	UU, all	June 2026 (M45)
	Final data management plan	UU, all	March 2027 (M54)

Deliverables:

D1.2 Data management plan, version 1 – M6 (UU)

D1.3 Data management plan update, version 2 – M36 (UU)

D1.5 Final data management plan, version 3 – M54 (UU)

Milestones:

MS3 Standard data formats implemented and database setup – M13 (UU)
(Partners agree on data formats and transfer of data into database.)

6 Annex

1 Dataset underlying 1 publication from CNRS:

Description	If the result is needed to validate the conclusions of a publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make your output available, either in digital or physical form?	Type of PID (if available)	PID (if available)	URL to repository landing page for result service/webpage hosting the result (required for datasets; recommended for other results)
Mineralisation, CFU, qPCR and alpha diversity data. Owner: CNRS	Data underlying publication: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2025.137690	DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17407293	https://zenodo.org/records/17407293

Type of publication	Peer-review	Type of PID(repository)	PID of deposited publication	Link to publication	Title of the publication	PID of publisher version of record	ISSN or eSSN	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number	Publisher	Year of publication	PID of Book (if book chapter)	Book title (if book chapter)	Was the publication available in open access through repository at the time of publication
Article in journal	Yes	DOI	https://zenodo.org/records/17909353		Development of a device to trap soil bacteria capable of degrading organic contaminants such as alkanes and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2025.137690	03043894	Audrey Vauloup, Aurélie Cébron	Journal of Hazardous Materials	491	Elsevier BV	February 2025			Yes

Table of Other produced Datasets:

Description	If the result is needed to validate the conclusions of a publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make your output available, either in digital or physical form?	Type of PID (if available)	PID (if available)	URL to repository landing page for result service/webpage hosting the result (required for datasets; recommended for other results)
Assembled genomes of whole-genome sequencing of bioremediation bacteria involved in degradation of petroleum hydrocarbons, cyanides and hexachlorocyclohexane. Owner: UGENT	It doesn't underpin publication	Other	NCBI/SRA Accession: PRJEB88388 ID: 1350058	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/1350058
Raw data (fastq.gz) and assembled genomes for Whole-genome sequencing of bioremediation bacteria involved in degradation of petroleum hydrocarbons, cyanides and hexachlorocyclohexane. Owner: UGENT	It doesn't underpin publication	Other	ENA Accession: PRJEB88388	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB88388
Microbiomes from HCH contaminated soil from Bitterfeld (DE) and Colleferro (IT). Owner: UNIFI	Publication in preparation, with DOI and licence CC-BY-NC	Other	NCBI/SRA Accession: PRJNA1117429 ID: 1117429	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/1117429
16S rRNA amplicon sequencing: BactoTrapS incubated in petroleum hydrocarbon polluted soils. Owner: CNRS	It doesn't underpin publication	Other	NCBI/SRA Accession: PRJNA1185691 ID: 1185691	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/1185691
Bacterial 16S rDNA sequence data: metabarcoding analysis of microbial community of 140 soil/groundwater samples of PHC sites. Owner: UHAS	It doesn't underpin publication	Other	NCBI/SRA Accession: PRJNA1099207 ID: 1099207	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/1099207

	A	B	C	D	E
1	type	description of data set	owner	source	dependence on re-used data
2			Who produced the data set and holds the licence?	How has the data been produced? E.g. experiments (raw data); interpretations/processing of experimental data; implementation of algorithms; modelling output	Has data been reused to produce this data set? If yes provide information on the re-used data.
3	Experimental results	<u>BactoTraps</u> incubation, monitoring and identification of captured bacteria. Data are: CO2 production in microcosms, DNA extraction, qPCR of 16S rDNA and functional genes, <u>metabarcoding</u> of 16S rDNA, 16S rDNA sequences from isolated bacterial strains...	<u>Aurélie Cébron</u> (CNRS) and <u>Audrey Vauloup</u> (CNRS)	Experiments (raw data); Interpretations/processing of experimental data	No
4	Experimental results	Microcosm incubation, monitoring and identification of the total and active bacterial community, and of the hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria. Data are: CO2 production in microcosms, measures of total petroleum hydrocarbon, DNA extraction, qPCR of 16S rDNA and functional genes, <u>metabarcoding</u> of 16S rDNA, <u>enrichments</u> growth curves and <u>TPH</u> degradation, 16S rDNA sequences from bacterial consortia...	<u>Aurélie Cébron</u> (CNRS) and <u>Jiangtao Qiao</u> (CNRS)	Experiments (raw data); Interpretations/processing of experimental data	No
5	Experimental results	Microcosm incubation, monitoring by <u>respirometry</u> (CO2 and O2 readings) and chemical analysis	<u>Cosimo Masini</u> (DND Biotech)	Experiments (raw data); Interpretations/processing of experimental data	No
6	Bacterial 16S rDNA sequence data	Axenic strains from high-throughput isolation and <u>dereplication</u> experiment that could (i) not be identified with MALDI-TOF MS or (ii) are interesting representatives for WGS	<u>Joni Elsmoortel</u> (UGENT), <u>Peter Vandamme</u> (UGENT)	Experiments (raw data); Interpretations/processing of experimental data	No
7	Other lab results (numerical data)	Total cell count and viability count data determined using <u>flow cytometry</u> , in relation to the storage experiment for microbial consortia	<u>Joni Elsmoortel</u> (UGENT), <u>Peter Vandamme</u> (UGENT)	Experiments (raw data); Interpretations/processing of experimental data	No
8	List of bacteria and cultures	Table of all isolates that were obtained from enriched samples	<u>Joni Elsmoortel</u> (UGENT), <u>Peter Vandamme</u> (UGENT)	Experiments (raw data); Interpretations/processing of experimental data	No
9	Biomass	Axenic strains from high-throughput isolation and <u>dereplication</u> experiment	<u>Joni Elsmoortel</u> (UGENT), <u>Peter Vandamme</u> (UGENT)	Experiments (raw data)	No
10	Experimental data of ALE experiment	Transparency data and evolution KPI (batch duration, average transparency, generation time)	<u>Julie Brouchon</u> and <u>Cyril Delattre</u> (Altar)	Experiment (raw data and analyzed data)	No
11	Experimental results	<u>Bitterfeld</u> : enrichment of 10 <u>microbiota</u> degrading the 4 isomers of <u>Hexachlorocyclohexane</u> , kinetics of depletion, Chemical data	<u>Simona Di Gregorio</u> , <u>Simone Becarelli</u> , <u>Riccardo Di Mambro</u> , <u>Giacomo Bernabei</u>	Experimental (raw data)	No
12	Experimental results	<u>COLLEFFERO</u> : enrichment of 12 <u>microbiota</u> degrading the 4 isomers of <u>Hexachlorocyclohexane</u> , kinetics of depletion, Chemical data	<u>Simona Di Gregorio</u> , <u>Simone Becarelli</u> , <u>Riccardo Di Mambro</u> , <u>Giacomo Bernabei</u>	Experimental (raw data)	No

	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P
1	role in Mibirem project	formats	software	Max size	number	purpose of use in the MIBIREM project	meta data standard	storage/repository	findable/link	publication	dissemination/accessibility
2	What is the context of the data set in the Mibirem project? E.g. In which work package and task was it produced? In which workpackage will it be used? Has	What is the format of the data? E.g. .csv , .biom , .fastq , .fasta , .xlsx , .txt , .doc , .docx , .tsv , .tiff , .jpeg , .png , .pdf , .svg , .rmd , .Rdata , .qmd , .r , .py , .sh	Is there a special software needed to open/read the data set?	What is the size of the data set? Particularly important is the order of magnitude i.e.	Number of files (if applicable)	Why are we re-using this data set? E.g. the data is need for performing task XX of the project.	What metadata standard is used.	Where is the data stored? Provide name and type of repository (e.g. type: domain, institutional, general,	Where is the data set located? Does a persistent identifier like doi exist? Provide a link/doi to the data.	Has this data led to a publication? If YES, provide link/doi to publication.	Is the data openly accessible? If the data is restricted, why? How will you restrict access? How will you enable access to those authorized?
3	Produced in WP2, T2.3 Reuse in WP2, T2.4	.csv .fastq .doc .txt	No	Mb	ca. 24			On Université de Lorraine repository named BUL		No	sequencing data will be deposited on SRA and NCBI other data will be available on Yoda
4	Produced in WP2, T2.2 Reuse in WP2, T2.4	.csv .fastq .doc	No	Mb	ca. 240			On Université de Lorraine repository named BUL		No	sequencing data have been deposited on SRA (accession number SAMN40577846 to SAMN40578036 (PRJNA1090889) other data will be available on Yoda
5	Produced in WP2, T2.2	.xlsx .pdf	No	Mb	ca. 10			DND Biotech drive		No	data will be available on Yoda
6	Produced in WP2 T2.4, reuse in WP3 T3.2	.fasta	No			Map sequence to genome for authenticity check	NA	repository named im_sequencing		No	YODA
7	Produced in WP3 T3.1	.csv, .fcs, .doc	ECM software or Rstudio	Gb	ca. 1500		NA	repository named im_flowcyometry		No	YODA
8	Produced in WP2 T2.4, reuse in WP3 T3.2 and WP2 T2.2	.csv	No			Selection of strains for WGS in T3.2	NA	On Ugent repository named im_mibirem		No	YODA
9	Produced in WP2 T2.4, reuse in WP3 T3.2	NA	NA	NA		Strains for WGS&deposit, and to build artificial consortium	NA	Ugent -80°C as liquid culture + 15% glycerol		No	
10	Produced in WP2 T2.5	.csv	No	1 Mb	14		NA	Altar's internal drive			
11	Produced in WP2 T2.4, reuse in WP3 T3.2	.xlsx	No	10Mb	1		NA	unipi INTERNAL DRIVE		No	YODA
12	Produced in WP2 T2.4, reuse in WP3 T3.2	.xlsx	No	10Mb	1		NA	unipi INTERNAL DRIVE		No	YODA

	A	B	C	D	E
1	type	description of data set	owner	source	dependence on re-used data
13	Experimental results	Bitterfeld: 16S rDNA metabarcoding of the microbial community of 10 soil samples, biological data	Simona Di Gregorio, Simone Becarelli, Riccardo Di Mambro, Giacomo Bernabei	Experimental (raw data)	No
14	Experimental results	Collefero: 16S rDNA metabarcoding of the microbial community of 11 soil samples, biological data	Simona Di Gregorio, Simone Becarelli, Riccardo Di Mambro, Giacomo Bernabei	Experimental (raw data)	No
15	Chemical data	chemical data analysis of Bitterfeld soil sample (10)	Simona Di Gregorio, Simone Becarelli, Riccardo Di Mambro, Giacomo Bernabei	external chemical analysis	No
16	experimental results	growth experiments measuring OD600, microscopic observation	Jessica Bevert	Experimental (raw data)	No
17	Bacterial 16S rDNA sequence data	metabarcoding analysis of microbial community of 140 soil/groundwater samples of PHC sites	Sofie Thijs	Experimental (raw data)	No
18	Experimental results	12 PAH degrading enrichment cultures from NL site Utrecht	Sofie Thijs	Experimental (raw data)	No
19	Experimental results	Axenic cultures of PAH-degrade from site Utrecht (+/-50 strains). Axenic cultures of PAH-degraders from site Lumco (+/- 50 strains), with data regarding their PAH degradation genes	Sofie Thijs	Experimental (raw data)	No
20	Bacterial whole-genome sequence data	Raw sequence data from pure isolates obtained from enrichment cultures	Eliza Depoorter (UGENT), Joni Elsmoortel (UGENT), Peter Vandamme (UGENT)	Experimental (raw data)	yes, based on "Table of all isolates that were obtained from enriched samples" from T2.4
21	Bacterial whole-genome sequence data	Annotated whole-genome sequences of pure isolates obtained from enrichment cultures	Eliza Depoorter (UGENT), Joni Elsmoortel (UGENT), Peter Vandamme (UGENT)	Processing of experimental data	yes, based on "Table of all isolates that were obtained from enriched samples" from T2.4
22	List of risk genes	List of antimicrobial resistance genes and virulence genes	Eliza Depoorter (UGENT), Joni Elsmoortel (UGENT), Peter Vandamme (UGENT)	Processing of experimental data	yes, based on annotated whole-genome sequences soils sampled in WP 1, cultures isolated in WP 2
23	Experimental results	lab tests on soil from pilot sites to select the best cultures	Cosimo Masini (DNR Biotech)	Experimental (raw data)	
24	Experimental results	cyanide degradation experiments	Thomas Reichenauer	Experimental (raw data)	no

	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P
1	role in Mibirem project	formats	software	Max size	number	purpose of use in the MIBIREM project	meta data standard	storage/repository	findable/link	publication	dissemination/accessibility
13	Produced in WP2 T2.1, data will be reused for WP5 T5.4	FASTQ	No	100 MB	30		NA	UOipj INTERNAL DRIVE		No	YODA
14	Produced in WP2 T2.1, data will be reused for WP5 T5.4	FASTQ	No	100MB	33		NA	UOipj INTERNAL DRIVE		No	YODA
15	Produced in WP1 T1.3, reuse in WP3-5	XLSX	No	100Mb	1		NA	UOipj INTERNAL DRIVE		No	YODA
16	Produced in WP2 T2.4	XLSX	No	1 Mb		identification of cultures for single strain picking and further use in WP3		SENSA server		No	will be deposited on YODA
17	produced in WP2	fastq and csv	No	Gb	140	Characterisation of microbiome of PHC sites	yes	NCBI_SRA	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/	No	deposited
18	produced in WP2	csv	No	Mb	12	Finding degradative strains	NA	UHAS google drive	na	to be	NA
19	produced in WP2	csv	No	Mb	100	Finding degradative strains	Na	UHAS google drive	na	to be	NA
20	produced in WP3 T3.2, will be re-used in T3.3	fastq.gz and .pod5	notepad and pod5	TB		Identification of cultures and analysis of degradation genes	ENA	UGent internal storage	not yet		will be deposited at ENA/NCBI (T3.3)
21	produced in WP3 T3.2, will be re-used in T3.3, T5.1 and T2.2	fasta and .qbk	notepad	GB		Identification of cultures and analysis of degradation genes	ENA	UGent internal storage	not yet		will be deposited at ENA/NCBI (T3.3)
22	produced in WP5 T5.1, re-used in T5.2	.xlsx	No	MB	30	Genome-based risk analysis of single isolates	NA	UGent internal storage			YODA
23	produced in WP5 T5.2	.xlsx	No	MB		selection of cultures for large scale testing	NA	DND Biotech drive	NA	to be	YODA
24	Produced in WP2 T2.5	.xlsx	No	1 Mb		use in WP3 and WP5		AIT server		to be	

Table of re-used datasets:

type	description of data set	owner	source	formats	software	Max size	number	purpose of use in the MIBIREM project	meta data standard	storage/ repository	findable/ link	publication	dissemination / accessibility
qPCR standards and standard curves	qPCR amplification results (Ct, calibration line coefficients, efficiency) for 16S rDNA, PAH-RHDa GN and GP, alkB, Catechol 1,2 and 2,3-dioxygenase genes	Aurélié Cébron (CNRS)	raw data	.csv,.pdf		500kb	6	performing T2.1, T2.3 and T3.1	no standard for metadata	locally			everyone if needed
protocole for DNA-SIP	DNA-SIP incubation and treatment (CSC ultracentrifugation, fractionation, validation) procedure	Aurélié Cébron (CNRS)	protocole	.txt,.pdf		500kb	1	performing T2.3	no standard for metadata	locally			everyone if needed
BactoTraits database use	Scripts to infer bacterial traits from bacterial diversity data	Aurélié Cébron (CNRS)	R scripts	.R		200ko	10	performing T2.1	no standard for metadata	locally			restricted to me
BactoTraits database	Bacterial traits database	Aurélié Cébron (CNRS)	data table	.csv,.xlsx		100Mo	1	performing T2.1	no standard for metadata	locally	https://doi.org/		all
Field measurement and description of site	soil and groundwater characteristics nad physico-chemical and contaminant measurements	CNRS, TAUW, SENSEA, AIT ... & site owner	report on sampling campain	.pdf		1 per site	1	WP1	no standard for metadata	locally			all
Field measurements groundwater	pH, EC, ntu of groundwater while sampling	AIT ... Owner: MIBIREM & site owner	data table	.csv,.xlsx		KB	1	sampling locations but mostly T1.3, T1.4, T4.1-T4.4, T5.2-T5.4	no standard for metadata	locally			all
Soil characteristics	Type of soil, geological information, location-specific characteristics	AIT ... Owner: MIBIREM & site owner	data table	.csv,.xlsx		MB	1	sampling locations but mostly T1.3, T1.4, T4.1-T4.4, T5.2-T5.4	no standard for metadata	locally			all
Coordinates	X/Y coordinates of sampling points	Owner: MIBIREM & site owner	data table	.csv,.xlsx		KB	1	sampling locations T1.2, T5.1-T5.4	no standard for metadata	locally			all
Pictures	Photos of the sites and sampling points	Producer: TAUW, SENSEA, AIT, ... Owner: MIBIREM & site owner	camera & smart phone	.jpg		MB	>10 pictures per site	T5.1-T5.4, T7.2	no standard for metadata	locally			all
field/soil characteristics	drilling profiles	Producer: SENSEA, ... Owner: SENSEA & site owner?	processing of data	.pdf		MB	< 10 profiles per site	T1.2, T1.3, T5.2-T5.4	no standard for metadata	locally			everyone if needed
experimental data	data of former degradation studies and remediation projects	Producer: SENSEA Owner: SENSEA & site owner	experiments+interpretation&processing od raw data	.csv,.xlsx		KB	5	T2.2, T2.3, T5.2-T5.4	no standard for metadata	locally			everyone if needed
Micobiome data	microbiome data of existing PHC culture	Producer: SENSEA Owner: SENSEA	interpretation/ processing od experimental data	.pdf		KB	1	T2.1	no standard for metadata	locally			everyone if needed
SILVA database	16S/18S SSU ribosomal database	Leibniz Institute DSMZ- German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures	here taxonomic markers for SSU are deposited by scientific community	.gz	264	Mb	1	T2.1, T4	no standard for metadata	arb-silva.de	https://www.	many	open
SILVA database	23S/ 28S LSU ribosomal database version 138.1 non redundant 99%	Leibniz Institute DSMZ- German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures	here taxonomic markers for LSU are deposited by scientific community	.gz	64	Mb	1	T4, T3.1	no standard for metadata	arb-silva.de	https://www.	many	open
UNITE database	ITS markers	unite community (non profit)	ITS markers from scientific community	.gz	120	Mb	1	T2.1, maybe t4	no standard for metadata	unite.ut.ee	https://doi.org/	many	open
Kraken 2 db	Curated set of prokaryotic and eukaryotic genome indexes.	Langmead lab, Johns Hopkins University.	Whole genome sequences freely available on NCBI GenBank.	.tar.gz	246	GB	>100k	T2.1, T2.3, T2.4	NCBI GenBank, ENA.	locally	https://ben	https://doi.org/	freely available
GTDB (Genome taxonomy database)	Curated archaeal and bacterial genome sequences and taxonomic information.	The University of Queensland, Australia.	Whole genome sequencing.	.tar.gz	66	GB	>300k	T2.1, T2.3, T2.4, T3.2	GTDB	locally	https://gtdb	https://doi.org/	freely available

MALDI-TOF MS Database	BDAL: reference library used for identification of isolates by pairwise comparison of measured spectrum to database	Bruker Daltonics (Germany)	processing of experimental MALDI-TOF MS data	.btmsp (Bruker file type), .txt, .xlsx, .xml	Bruker Daltonics software: Flex Analysis and MBT Compass Explorer	MB	>10K	performing T2.4	no standard for metadata	locally	No identifier	Commercial database under license, restricted to LM-UGent staff	
MALDI-TOF MS Database	LM UGENT ID: reference library used for identification of isolates by pairwise comparison of measured spectrum to database	LM-UGent	processing of experimental MALDI-TOF MS data	.btmsp (Bruker file type), .txt, .xlsx, .xml	Bruker Daltonics software: Flex Analysis and MBT Compass Explorer	MB	>5K	performing T2.4	no standard for metadata	locally	No identifier	In-house database, restricted to LM-UGent staff	
EzBioCloud database	Standardized 16S rRNA gene sequence database of reference taxa	CJ Bioscience, Inc. (Korea)	Processing of whole genome sequencing data					performing T2.4	NCBI	https://www.ezbiocloud.net/ domain	EzBioCloud web server	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf92	Free for use by researchers affiliated with non-profit academic institutions
Microbiome data	Functional PHC-degrading microbial consortium	Producer: SENSA Owner: SENSA	Functional PHC-degrading microbial consortium				1	performing T3.1	no standard for metadata				
Microbiome data	Functional HCH- or cyanide-degrading microbial consortium	Producer: ? Owner: ? (MIBIREM partner)	Functional HCH or cyanide-degrading microbial consortium				2	performing T3.1	no standard for metadata				
checkM database	Curated set of marker genes from reference genomes	The University of Queensland, Australia.	Processing of whole genome sequencing data	.tar.gz		GB	33	performing T3.2	no standard for metadata	locally	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf92	freely available	
TYGS	Curated set of type strain genomes	Leibniz Institute DSMZ (Germany)	Processing of whole genome sequencing data					performing T3.2	no standard for metadata	https://tygs.dsmz.de/ domain	TYGS web server	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf92 and https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.004332 and https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf92	Free for academic purposes
LPSN	List of Prokaryotic names with Standing in Nomenclature	Leibniz Institute DSMZ (Germany)	data table	.csv		MB	1	performing T3.2	no standard for metadata	locally	https://lpsn.dsmz.de/	ab902	freely available
UniProt	Database of protein sequences	EMBL-EBI	Processing of experimental data and whole genome sequencing data	.gz		MB		performing T3.2	no standard for metadata	locally	https://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf92	
antismash	Database of secondary metabolite gene clusters	Technical University of Denmark (DTU) and University of Wageningen (Netherlands)	Processing of whole genome sequencing data	.tar.gz		GB		performing T3.2 and T5.1	no standard for metadata	locally	https://dls.dsmz.de/	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf92	freely available
eggNOG- mapper	Database of functional annotations and orthology relationships	EMBL Heidelberg (Germany)	Processing of whole genome sequencing data	.db, .pkl, .dmd		GB	3	performing T3.2 and T5.1	no standard for metadata	locally	http://eggno-mapper.com/	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf92	freely available
(comprehensive antibiotic resistance database)	Database of antibiotic resistance genes	McMaster University	Processing of whole genome sequencing data	.tar.bz2		MB		performing T3.2 and T5.1	no standard for metadata	locally	https://card.mcmaster.ca/	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf92	Free for academic purposes
AMRFinderPlus database	Database of antibiotic resistance genes	NCBI	Processing of whole genome sequencing data	.tar.gz		MB		performing T3.2 and T5.1	no standard for metadata	locally	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/AMRFinderPlus/	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf92	freely available
Virulence Factor database (VFDB)	Database of virulence genes	Institute of Pathogen Biology (China)	Processing of whole genome sequencing data	.gz		MB		performing T3.2 and T5.1	no standard for metadata	locally	http://www.cafbio.com/	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf92	freely available
Microbiome data	Table of all isolates that were obtained from enriched samples	UGent	Processing of MALDI-TOF MS and 16S rRNA gene sequencing data	.xlsx		MB		performing T2.4, T3.2 and T2.2	no standard for metadata	locally			everyone if needed
experimental data	Annotated whole genome sequences of best-degrading isolates	UGent	Processing of raw whole genome sequencing data	.fasta and .gbk		GB		performing T3.2 and T5.1	no standard for metadata	ENA			everyone if needed